

Data Table 2. Distribution of viable tetrad classes for each tested genotype.						
	4 spore tetrads	3 spore tetrads	2 spore tetrads	1 spore tetrads	0 spore tetrads	Total tetrads
Hybrid, wild type	0	0	0	5	264	269
Hybrid, pCLB2-MSH2	0	0	7	14	199	220
Hybrid, pCLB2-SGS1	19	27	79	114	295	534
Hybrid, pCLB2-SGS1 pCLB2-MSH2	108	245	477	539	668	2037
<i>S.paradoxus</i> , wild type	75	19	6	0	0	100
<i>S.cerevisiae</i> , wild type	44	48	7	1	0	100
<i>S.paradoxus</i> , pCLB2-SGS1	61	31	7	0	1	100
<i>S.cerevisiae</i> , pCLB2-SGS1	55	21	17	6	0	99
<i>S. par.</i> , pCLB2-SGS1 pCLB2-MSH2	78	9	11	2	0	100
<i>S. cer.</i> , pCLB2-SGS1 pCLB2-MSH2	38	23	22	7	0	90